

*Detecting significant lexico-grammatical patterns : the
MotiveR script for stylistic analysis in French*

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Abstract

Stylometry has traditionally focused on authorship verification and text dating through quantitative analyses. However, with advancements in computer science and the emergence of corpus linguistics and Digital Humanities, there's a shift towards qualitative analyses characterizing text properties. This evolution leads to the development of corpus stylistics, combining traditional rigor with large quantified data. MotiveR is introduced as a tool for corpus-based stylistics, designed initially for French but adaptable to other languages. Unlike traditional methods, MotiveR identifies lexico-grammatical patterns termed "motifs", offering a nuanced approach to stylistic analysis. It bridges the gap between stylometry's quantitative focus and stylistics' qualitative examination, enabling users to interpret results systematically while being accessible to non-computer scientists. Built under tidy standards, MotiveR allows interoperability and customization, promising ongoing enrichment of functionalities.

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Introduction

For a long time, the objectives of stylometry were authorship verification, or the dating of texts, the similarity (generally lexical) between several texts. From now on, with the development of the possibilities offered by computer science, and the advent of corpus linguistics or Digital Humanities, more qualitative analyses (based on quantitative results) are no longer only envisaged, but actually carried out in order to characterize the properties of a text (or of a textual genre, or the textual production of an author). A corpus stylistics can thus be developed: it retains the rigor and the degree of precision of traditional stylistics, while relying on large quantified data.

In this short article, we would like to present a tool dedicated to corpus-based stylistics. This script, MotiveR, was designed for French but can be easily adapted to another language. This tool, which takes the form of an R script, has the function of identifying in texts, not lexemes or repeated segments, but characteristic lexico-grammatical patterns. These patterns are called "motifs" (cf. Legallois and al. 2018). After having explained what a pattern is, we devote the article to the presentation of the different functions offered by the script. Our objective here is not to propose a precise stylistic analysis of a corpus, but simply to give the reader the main elements of the MotiveR script - a script that he will be able to transform for an application to his own data. Some results will be given for illustrative purposes: they come from an analysis of a corpus of detective novels (all of which have received the "Quai des Orfèvres" prize) published between 1992 and 1998.

1 Motifs and MotiveR

MotiveR is a program for stylistics in French built around a set of computer functions using the R programming language (R Core Team, 2020) to identify idiosyncratic stylistic "motifs" within a corpus. It is available in open-source.

A motif is defined as a lexico-grammatical pattern characteristic of a text. Unlike the method of lexical n-grams (or lexical bundles), which are considered too specific, and the method of part of speech n-grams, which is considered too schematic, the method of motifs aims to model texts by identifying patterns whose elements are mixed in nature: fixed forms, lemmas, and morpho-syntactic and semantic categories (Legallois, Charnois and Poibeau, 2016; Legallois, Charnois and Larjavaara, 2018).

For example, sequences of pos-grams like:

(1) DET NC PREP DET NC PREP DET ADJ

are too general or abstract to identify recurrences that can be interpreted as the style of an author or of a textual genre. On the other hand, repeated segments or lexical bundles like:

(2) la pression de son genou contre le sien / le contact de ses lèvres contre
les siennes (*the pressure of his knee against hers / the contact of her lips against
his own*)

are lexically too specific, since there are here two different realizations of the same pattern. To capture this pattern, the text must undergo a specific annotation from which a computer system will be able to identify a recurrence. Thus, MotiveR performs a specific annotation, which mixes morpho-syntactic categories, lemmas and fixed forms (for grammatical words like prepositions). Thus, an annotation like:

(3) le NC de DETPOSS NC contre le sien (*the NC of DETPOSS NC against
his own*).

corresponds to the repeated segments of (2).

This segment is a motif if it is statistically characteristic of a text compared to other texts. A motif is therefore a unit that has a "specific granularity: it is more schematic than a word-ngram. By applying regular expressions, MotiveR modifies the annotation performed by UDPipe:

- It keeps the invariable forms (prepositions, conjunctions, frequent adverbs), etc.
- It lemmatizes frequent verbs (auxiliaries, modal verbs, aspect verbs); reduce pronominal forms to a canonical form.
- It preserves POS labels (common noun, proper noun, verb (+tense), infinitive, adjective, etc.).
- It semantically annotates certain nouns and adverbs: adverbs of manner, abstract nouns, nouns expressing a body part.

Then, MotiveR tokenizes the corpus into ngrams (the size is to be defined) and thus allows to perform different calculations such as TF-idf for the calculation of specificities. Once the statistically overused patterns have been defined, MotiveR returns to the texts: it proposes matches of the different patterns. The functionalities of MotiveR are therefore the following:

1. Morphosyntactic and morphological tagging in tidy format via UDPipe (Straka, 2018).
2. Transformation into patterns via regular expressions (rule system). MotiveR will retrieve some of the information from the labelling to transform the texts of the corpus into patterns. The program keeps invariable forms (prepositions, conjunctions, frequent adverbs), the lemma of auxiliaries, reduces pronominal forms to a canonical form, keeps certain morphosyntactic labels (common noun, proper noun, verb (+ time), infinitive, adjective, adverbs not previously qualified), and semantically annotates certain nouns and adverbs: manner adverbs, abstract nouns, nouns expressing a part of the body.
3. Choice of the number of n-grams. This choice impacts all the following functions, i.e. it is necessary to stick to it or to restart the process from there if one wishes to change the length of the patterns.
4. Frequency histograms (absolute / relative).
5. Term Frequency-inverse document frequency (TF-IDF) (Robertson, 2004).

Figure 1: Motifs calculated according to the TF-IDF.

6. Principal Component Analysis (Husson, Lê and Pagès, 2009).

Figure 2: Example of a Principal Component Analysis via MotiveR.

7. Calculation of the density of a motif within a text of the corpus.
8. Computation of the evolution of a form within a corpus.
9. Calculation of specificities (Lafon, 1984, Bertels and Speelman 2013) :

$$\text{mode}(\text{card}\{A \in V | A \in p\} = f) = \frac{(F + 1) \times (t + 1)}{T + 2}$$

where:

- A is the identified motif
- V : the set of possible motifs
- p : the part of the corpus considered, (a text)
- f : the total frequency of the motif in the part
- F: the total frequency of the motif in the corpus
- t: the total number of motifs in the part
- T : the total number of motifs in the corpus

10. Return to texts:

- On all motifs
- On one motif

Show entries

Search:

	id	contexte_gauche	motif	contexte_droit	Oeuvre	motifs	n	total	nrel	Balzac-Goriot.txt-ut8.txt	Flaubert-Bovary.txt-ut8.txt	Huysmans-Rebours.txt-ut8.txt
1	717	verrait là que de les pensions ou	de les Institutions de la	misère ou de l'ennui , de la	Balzac-Goriot.txt-ut8.txt	de le NC de le	44	110662	0.000397607128011422	-1.4272	-0.5648	2.4034
2	1450	en bonne intelligence de les cochons ,	de les poules de les	lapins et à le de laquelle s' élève	Balzac-Goriot.txt-ut8.txt	de le NC de le	44	110662	0.000397607128011422	-1.4272	-0.5648	2.4034
3	4736	de son enfant . Malheureusement la veuve	de le Commissaire-Ordonnateur de les	armées de la République possédait rien à le	Balzac-Goriot.txt-ut8.txt	de le NC de le	44	110662	0.000397607128011422	-1.4272	-0.5648	2.4034
4	4739	. Malheureusement la veuve de le Commissaire-Ordonnateur	de les armées de la	République possédait rien à le monde que son	Balzac-Goriot.txt-ut8.txt	de le NC de le	44	110662	0.000397607128011422	-1.4272	-0.5648	2.4034
5	8037	y eut entre monsieur Goriot et madame	de l' Ambermesnil de les	choses telles que la comtesse ne voulut même	Balzac-Goriot.txt-ut8.txt	de le NC de le	44	110662	0.000397607128011422	-1.4272	-0.5648	2.4034
6	8397	avait l' habitude de ne pas sortir	de le cercle de les	événements , et de ne pas juger leurs	Balzac-Goriot.txt-ut8.txt	de le NC de le	44	110662	0.000397607128011422	-1.4272	-0.5648	2.4034
7	13108	ligne de lumière tracée à le bas	de la porte de le	père Goriot . Eugène craignit que son voisin	Balzac-Goriot.txt-ut8.txt	de le NC de le	44	110662	0.000397607128011422	-1.4272	-0.5648	2.4034
8	14972	-ce qu' on sait ? Il fait	de les trafics de les	cinq diables . J' ai trop dormi ,	Balzac-Goriot.txt-ut8.txt	de le NC de le	44	110662	0.000397607128011422	-1.4272	-0.5648	2.4034
9	21221	phrase était une traduction claire et intelligible	de les regards de le	jeune homme impertinemment fier que la comtesse Anastasie	Balzac-Goriot.txt-ut8.txt	de le NC de le	44	110662	0.000397607128011422	-1.4272	-0.5648	2.4034
10	22134	dans la liquidation qu' il a faite	de la compagnie de les	Indes . Monsieur votre grand-oncle ne commandait pas	Balzac-Goriot.txt-ut8.txt	de le NC de le	44	110662	0.000397607128011422	-1.4272	-0.5648	2.4034

Showing 1 to 10 of 165 entries

Previous 2 3 4 5 ... 17 Next

Figure 3: Example of return to texts (motif : de le NC de le).

The following diagram summarizes the steps:

MotiveR Workflow

2 Some illustrative results

We would like to show some results, for purely illustrative purposes. The selected corpus includes five novels, published between 1992 and 1998:

- 1998, *La Danse du soleil*, Michel Sibra.
- 1996, *Rage de flic*, Gilbert Schlogel.
- 1994, *Une belle garce*, Jean-Louis Viot.
- 1993, *Pièces détachées*, Gérard Delteil.
- 1992, *Razzia sur l'antique*, Louis-Marie Brézac.

These novels won the Prix du Quai des Orfèvres - a literary prize awarded annually to the best crime novel of the year by a jury composed of senior judges, qualified police officers, former directors of "36", lawyers and journalists. This corpus is very small but MotiveR can be applied without any problem to the analysis of several dozen texts. Thanks to MotiveR, we have calculated the specific patterns for each novel (by calculating the specificities); here are some of them:

— "**ce être un NC ADJ**" is a (slightly) favored motif (specificity of 3.75) in the novel *Pièces détachées* by Gérard Delteil (1993) to express evaluations:

(4) Il adorait causer et c'était un conteur-né (*He loved to talk and was a born storyteller*)

(5) Mais elle nous charriait quand même. C'est une affaire grave : un crime, dis-je. (*But she was laughing at us anyway. This is a serious matter: a crime, I said.*)

(6) C'est une accusation grave, souligna Rinaldi à l'issue de cette pause (*This is a serious accusation,* " said Rinaldi after the break)

(7) C'est une fille hypersensible qui aimait beaucoup son père. (*She is a hypersensitive girl who loved her father very much.*)

— "**. NP VPS le NC**" is clearly overused in *La Danse du soleil* by Michel Sibra (1998) (specificity of 9.05). The pattern begins a sentence: it contains a transitive verb in the simple past tense. Most often the pattern follows on from another action (by coordination or juxtaposition):

(8) Skolvan contourna le commissaire et se pencha sur le cadavre. (*Skolvan walked around the commissioner and leaned over the corpse*).

(9) Hubert fouilla la portière de sa voiture et sortit une carte de la région. (*Hubert searched the door of his car and took out a map of the region*).

(10) Skolvan referma le livre, le serra sur sa poitrine. (*Skolvan closed the book and clutched it to his chest*).

— "**. NP PRES DETPOSS NC**" is a motif very close to the previous one, but the verb tense is in the present and the nature of the determiner (here a possessive) changes. This motive is overused in *Une belle garce*, Jean-Louis Viot (1994) (specificity of 9.99):

(11) Noget écrase sa cigarette, en rallume une autre (*Noget puts out his cigarette, lights another one*).

(12) Mallet ouvre son bureau, sans entrain, suspend son blouson, ressort baguenauder. (*Mallet opens his office, without enthusiasm, hangs up his jacket, goes out to wander*).

(13) Coussinel vide son verre, le repose. (*Coussinel empties his glass, puts it back*).

- "**le NC PRES le NCCOR**" is a motif favored by *Une belle garce*, Jean-Louis Viot (1994) (specificity of 7.47); it is related to the body movements of the characters:

(14) Et vous ? Le policier hausse les épaules. (*What about you? The policeman shrugs his shoulders*).

(15) La brune agite les bras, s'empêtre dans la bandoulière de son sac. (*The brunette waves her arms, gets tangled in the shoulder strap of her bag*).

(16) le divisionnaire relève la tête pour lui faire part de ses réflexions. (*the divisional officer raises his head to share his thoughts with him*).

- "**le NC avoir être PPAS**" is an overused motif in *Razzia sur l'antique*, Louis-Marie Brézac (1992) (specificity of 4.38). It is a passive form in the past tense :

(17) L'état-major a été avisé depuis bientôt deux heures. (*The staff was notified almost two hours ago*).

(18) le cadavre avait été déposé, sous les yeux de Jonquet et de Lucas. *the corpse had been deposited, under the eyes of Jonquet and Lucas*.

(20) Les tiroirs avaient été ôtés et leur contenu déversé. (*The drawers had been removed and their contents poured out*).

Some patterns, although overused, are not interpretable: they are those which, for example, are "cut" by punctuation marks (for example, "**the NC . NP VIMP**"). They do not constitute motifs. One can only observe that in a certain text (*Rage de flic*, Gilbert Schlogel (1996)), the author has a tendency (compared to others) to start a sentence with a proper noun and a verb in the imperfect tense, when the preceding sentence ends with a common noun). This information could however be useful in an analysis of the structuring of texts.

3 Conclusion

MotiveR is situated at the frontier of stylometric and stylistic questions and is intended to be used by both disciplines: as a complement to stylometry, whose orientations are essentially quantitative, seeking to answer questions such as: what are the subjects addressed

by a given text? By whom was it written? When was it written? But also as a complement to stylistics, whose orientations are essentially qualitative, focusing on particular and specific facts of language: is this form significant for this author or this text? How can we interpret this form as a style of this author, text, genre or corpus? Contrary to many approaches in digital humanities and in big data which stick to distant reading, but also in contrast to stylistics which sticks to singular facts of language, MotiveR proposes a mixed method, relying on statistical methods but nevertheless enabling a systematic return to the texts to interpret the results. MotiveR is intended to be used by a non-computer scientist with minimal computer skills and is presented in the form of linked functions, allowing the user to go from raw texts, to statistical visualizations, and finally return to the texts in their original form from the identified patterns. It is however built entirely under the tidy standards, which allow an easier interoperability with other functions or programs (TXM, Stylo package, etc.), as well as an exit from the pipeline at each step. MotiveR is an evolving program whose functionalities will be enriched over time (constitution of a library, enrichment of functionalities, e.g. more flexible choice of ngrams, consideration of multiple locutions and words, reinforced interoperability, graphic interfaces). It can be easily adapted for other languages than French.

4 Appendices

- **License:** Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License.
- **Repository location:** <https://github.com/Malichot/MotiveR>.
- **Requirements:** The preparation of the corpus must respect two requirements: the texts must be in a specific folder in .txt format and the encoding must be UTF-8. After that, you just have to retrieve the content of the program from the GitLab repository and open the general process that calls up all the functions in the same script.
- **Authors roles:**
 - Antoine Silvestre de Sacy: Conceptualization, Writing.
 - Dominique Legallois: Supervision, Writing.

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